

ISW

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials
Grant Agreement No. 101016503

Policy brief: Accelerating the uptake of in silico trials in healthcare

You can cite this document by using the DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14534365](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534365). Geris, L., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Rangarajan, J. R., Biasin, E., Van Hoyweghen, I., & Viceconti, M. (2024). Policy brief: Accelerating the uptake of in silico trials in healthcare. Zenodo.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016503

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Executive Summary

A policy brief is a concise document that articulates information and analysis, offering evidence-based recommendations to address a specific (policy) issue¹. Typically (but not solely) targeted at policymakers, it aims to succinctly convey the key aspects of a problem, present viable solutions, and provide a rationale for the proposed course of action. The document is characterised by brevity, clarity, and objectivity, serving as a tool to inform decision-makers about the complexities of a given (policy) challenge and to guide them in making informed choices.

The information incorporated in this document stems from a range of stakeholder engagement activities conducted as part of the In Silico World's "Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement" activities, including a desk review, a Delphi survey, a clinical survey, three geographically spread focus groups, a final Responsible Research and Innovation workshop, and several consensus processes run on various topics through the In Silico World Community of Practice, an online forum that sees the participation of over 700 experts from academia, industry, governmental agencies, healthcare providers, etc. The valuable insights acquired through this extensive engagement with diverse stakeholders have elucidated the crucial actions required to reduce the barriers hindering the advancement and uptake of in silico trial technologies. These findings align seamlessly with the overarching objective of the In Silico World project.

The policy brief outlines the essential engagement strategies for each stakeholder group. It starts with the **context of the letter**, providing background information on the topic of in silico trials, its **stakeholders** (academia, industry, healthcare providers, regulators, HTA and payers, policymakers, patients and public) and their **public values**, as obtained from a Delphi survey. Next, the **challenges** are listed as they have been identified at the project onset and through stakeholder engagement activities such as surveys and focus groups. This is followed by a discussion of the **co-creation of governance solutions**. In the context of this policy brief, governance refers to the structured framework through which research and innovation are managed and coordinated. Possible governance mechanisms entail regulations, principles, standards, securitisation efforts, codes of conduct, impact assessments, or value statements.

Based on this information, **general action points and policy recommendations** are formulated, followed by specific action points for each stakeholder category independently. The key messages of this policy brief are as follows.

- Promote in silico medicine through science communication and outreach activities with a wide range of stakeholders.
- Educate and train all stakeholders, with a focus on clinicians, engineers, and the public.
- Recognise and involve patient expertise.

¹ Food Security Communications Toolkit. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Rome, 2011. ISBN 978-92-5-106858-8

- Address malicious uses and ethical responsibilities, acknowledge limitations of the technologies, and detail context-of-use for building trust by creating ethical manifestos or codes of conduct.
- Foster interdisciplinary collaboration with diverse stakeholders to ensure the development is in line with the expectations, needs and values of all stakeholders while ensuring inclusion of underrepresented populations. Integrate social sciences and humanities (SSH) for a comprehensive understanding of ethical, legal, and social concerns.
- Promote the transitional adoption of VV-40 in Europe as well as the development of an EU-harmonized standard.
- Foster collaborations with regulators and policymakers. Develop a specific set of recommendations to lower regulatory barriers.

1 Policy brief: “Accelerating the uptake of in silico trials in healthcare”

1.1 Context: In Silico Trials

In Silico Medicine refers to the exploitation of modelling and simulation technologies in healthcare. The term "In Silico Trial" refers to the use of computer modelling and simulation for assessing the safety and efficacy of various medical products, including drugs, medical devices, and advanced therapy medicinal products². Traditionally, the evaluation of safety and efficacy has relied on experimental methods such as in vitro and ex vivo tests, animal experimentation, and clinical trials in humans. However, several factors prompted the integration of computational models into the evidence-generation paradigm. In particular, in vitro and ex vivo tests are time-consuming, ethical concerns surround animal experimentation, and clinical trials are expensive, time-intensive, and sometimes also pose ethical concerns. The high costs and prolonged time-to-market not only result in elevated selling prices but also contribute to under-representation and discrimination, considering factors such as gender, age, ethnicity, the rarity of conditions, and wealth. Moreover, many traditional experimental methods primarily serve to reject a hypothesis, demonstrating the lack of safety or efficacy/effectiveness of a product while offering limited insights into how to enhance the safety and efficacy/effectiveness of such products.

1.2 The stakeholders of in silico trials and their public values

The main actors related to the development and adoption of in silico trial technologies and the target audience of this policy brief are the following (Figure 1):

- Researchers in the in silico field: in academia and non-profit labs
- Biomedical and simulation industries: MedTech, Pharma, Software
- Healthcare professionals: clinicians, nurses etc.
- Regulators and conformity assessment bodies (Notified Bodies)
- Institutional stakeholders: health authorities; payers; ministries of research, industry, and healthcare; research and innovation funding agencies; healthcare and social charities; other interested governmental and nongovernmental organisations
- Patients and carers
- The public at large: EU citizens, taxpayers.

² Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, Courcelles E, Curreli C, Famaey N, Geris L, Horner M, Jori MC, Kulesza A, Loewe A, Neidlin M, Reiterer M, Rousseau CF, Russo G, Sonntag SJ, Voisin EM, Pappalardo F. Possible Contexts of Use for In Silico Trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review. IEEE J Biomed Health Inform. 2021 Oct;25(10):3977-3982. doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469. Epub 2021 Oct 5. PMID: 34161248.

Interactions with the stakeholders were streamlined according to the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) as articulated by Guston (2014)³, to systematically recognise and address social and ethical impediments across the innovation continuum with the overarching objective of augmenting the societal integration and responsiveness of innovations, in accordance with the perspectives outlined by Stilgoe et al. (2014)⁴, Landeweerd et al. (2013)⁵, and the European Commission (2013)⁶.

Through a Delphi survey⁷, in silico trial developers and users produced a list of public values or guiding principles about the development and uptake of in silico trial technologies (Figure 2):

- Autonomy, Data privacy and management, Informed consent
- 'Do no harm', Efficiency, Prevention, Personalised treatment
- Independence from technology, Trust in technology, Accountability, Responsibility
- Solidarity, Equality, Justice
- Animal well-being and human safety, Environmental considerations

Using these principles resulted in meaningful dialogues with stakeholders during engagement activities, including surveys⁸ and one-on-one stakeholder interactions such as focus groups⁹. These activities and conversations allowed us to identify perceived challenges and needs which were used as input for the Responsible Research and Innovation

³ Guston, David H. "Understanding 'Anticipatory Governance.'" *Social studies of science* 44, no. 2 (2014): 218–242.

⁴ Stilgoe, Jack, Richard Owen, and Phil Macnaghten. "Developing a Framework for Responsible Innovation." *Research policy* 42, no. 9 (2013): 1568–1580.

⁵ Landeweerd, Laurens, David Townend, Jessica Mesman, and Ine Van Hoyweghen. "Reflections on Different Governance Styles in Regulating Science: A Contribution to 'Responsible Research and Innovation.'" *Life sciences, society and policy* 11, no. 1 (2015): 8–8.

⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Communication, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Responsible research and innovation (RRI), science and technology – Report, Publications Office, 2013, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/45726>

⁷ Van Oudheusden, M., Lesage, R., Geris, L., Van Hoyweghen, I. (2023). Internal Survey for ISW General Assembly: A Delphi Approach - <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740390>

⁸ Lesage R, Van Oudheusden M, Schievano S, Van Hoyweghen I, Geris L, Capelli C. Mapping the use of computational modelling and simulation in clinics: A survey. *Front Med Technol.* 2023 Apr 17;5:1125524. doi: 10.3389/fmedt.2023.1125524. PMID: 37138727; PMCID: PMC10150234.

⁹ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievrouw, E., Geris, L., Van Hoyweghen, I. (2023). In Silico World WP5 Stakeholder Engagement - Focus Groups Analysis Report - <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740366>

process, resulting in the identification of tangible action points for each stakeholder category (Figure 3).¹⁰

1.3 Challenges for accelerating uptake of in silico trial

technologies

Based on a first analysis of the status of in silico trials, several challenges were identified as possibly impeding the rapid adoption of In Silico Trials¹¹.

Challenges related to the technical development of in silico trials

Lack of Advanced Models: Scarcity of predictive models that are both advanced and robust enough to facilitate the reduction, refinement, or replacement of clinical trials required for certifying new medical products. This encompasses challenges in supporting development, transitioning from data-driven to knowledge-based models¹², and vice versa.

Lack of Independent Validation Collections: Absence of widely available collections of curated medical data specifically tailored for the development (e.g., for Analytic AI predictors) and validation of In Silico Trials technologies.

Poor Scalability and Efficiency: The insufficient scalability of most In Silico Trials models, coupled with a lack of efficient computing for large-scale population models within user-friendly, secure, and trusted environments.

Challenges related to the implementation of in silico trials in healthcare settings

No Clear Regulatory Pathways: The absence of clear regulatory pathways necessitates the generalisation of credibility assessments, as proposed in ASME VV-40¹³, to encompass models used

¹⁰ Elisa Elhadj, Zita Van Horenbeeck, Elisa Lievevrouw & Ine Van Hoyweghen (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in in silico medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

¹¹ Viceconti M, De Vos M, Mellone S, Geris L. Position paper From the digital twins in healthcare to the Virtual Human Twin: a moon-shot project for digital health research. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2023 Oct 11;PP. doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2023.3323688. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 37819828.

¹² Geris L, Rousseau C F., Noailly J, Afshari P, Auffret M, Chu WY, De Cunha-Burgman M, Lafon Y, ... Waterkeyn A. (2022). WHITE PAPER: the role of Artificial Intelligence within in silico medicine. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8064147>

¹³ Assessing Credibility of Computational Modeling through Verification and Validation: Application to Medical Devices V&V 40 (2018). American Society for Mechanical Engineers (ASME - Publisher), ISBN: 9780791872048.

for evaluating pharmaceutical and combinatory products. This involves the harmonisation of VV-40 within the CEN¹⁴ standardisation framework, "First in kind" qualification of In Silico Trials methods for medicines evaluation with EMA, exploration of new regulatory pathways for class III medical devices and pharmaceutical products, facilitating a substantial reduction in human experimentation via In Silico Trials technologies, and the adoption of rigorous post-marketing surveillance to monitor the validity of in silico predictions as new products are adopted.

Challenges related to the general development and uptake of in silico trials in society

Lack of Trained Workforce: A shortage of opportunities for training and re-training personnel with the requisite technical skills for In Silico Trials, applicable across industry, regulatory agencies, research hospitals, and other relevant domains.

Poorly Informed Stakeholders: Inadequate and inaccurate information dissemination to all stakeholders, including policymakers, patients, doctors, regulators, healthcare payers, Contract Research Organisations (CRO), technology providers, and executives of biomedical companies. This underscores the need for the development and application of a rigorous risk-benefit evaluation framework to assess the adoption of In Silico Trials technologies from the perspective of each stakeholder.

In addition to these above-defined challenges, dedicated stakeholder engagement activities such as focus groups and surveys probed the perspectives, interests, and expectations of diverse groups of stakeholders who wield influence over the development and adoption of in silico trial technologies.^{15,1617} This resulted in the identification of additional challenges related to technical, ethical, legal and, in particular, social issues.

Navigating bias: Bias in in silico trials is associated with the input phase of the in silico development workflow through the input data being used as well as model design choices. However, concerns related to bias also exist surrounding access to the final product. At the same time, in silico technologies can minimise biased input or training data through virtual cohorts that mitigate social exclusion.

Responsibility: Developers of in silico technologies generally share a sense of responsibility in the development of computational models, yet the extent of the individual responsibility is unclear. There is no legal framework that clearly defines the personal responsibility of the model developer

¹⁴ European Committee for Standardization (CEN, French: Comité Européen de Normalisation)

¹⁵ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievrouw, E., Geris, L., and Van Hoyweghen, I. Rep. In Silico World *WP5 Stakeholder Engagement - Focus Groups Analysis Report*, 2023. Available via public repository: <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740366>.

¹⁶ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievrouw, E., Geris, L., and Van Hoyweghen, I. Rep. In Silico World *WP 5 Responsible Research and Innovation Workshop Report*, 2023. Available via public repository: <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740365>.

¹⁷ Elisa Elhadj, Zita Van Horenbeeck, Elisa Lievrouw & Ine Van Hoyweghen (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in in silico medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

as it exists in (other) medical product development processes. There is no overall framework that clarifies the responsibility and delegation process.

Trust: Trust is crucial for shaping the future of in silico medicine as the foundation for progress and collaboration. This entails the need for transparency as well as clear and effective stakeholder engagement throughout the entire research and innovation process. This also requires the proven, documented competence of the model developer, the transparency of the model developing process and related quality control and quality assurance steps. Policy and regulatory stakeholders, who set and govern the regulatory pathway for emerging in silico trial technologies, seek validations to evaluate the effectiveness and reliability. The need to build trust between the technology developers and regulators demands transparency but also building relevant expertise on verification and validation methods for all relevant stakeholders.

Changing landscape of expertise: In silico medicine could challenge the traditional notions of expertise, leading to discussions on the roles of patients and clinicians. There is a clear need to recognise patients as active agents in developing in silico trial technologies, though the extent to which this needs to happen is still unclear. With increased knowledge and empowerment of patients, the traditional hierarchy of expertise is set to shift the roles of healthcare professionals and patients, whereby in silico medicine could facilitate an inclusive healthcare journey. Recognising the significance of this shift, effective engagement and communication with the public are crucial to foster understanding, trust, and ensure a connection between advancements in in silico medicine and the broader community. Healthcare professionals and regulators who are at the forefront of adopting in silico technologies are expected to go beyond their traditional skill set and leverage these innovations to support their clinical/regulatory decision-making.

Representation in modelling and the quest for an 'integrated virtual human twin': The concepts of "holistic modelling" in in silico medicine pose several challenges related to the desirability and achievability of building a comprehensive, integrated virtual human twin. Additional challenges relate to the broader sociological considerations of this in terms of representation and the potential social exclusion.

Definitional issues: Definitional issues still exist to date, with different stakeholders sometimes using different terminologies to indicate similar concepts or grouping different concepts under the same term. A typical example is the intersection of in silico medicine and artificial intelligence (AI). AI is one of the approaches on the spectrum of in silico medicine technologies but is frequently considered as either something fully separate or fully synonymous. There is a need to improve communication and streamline terminology to facilitate meaningful collaboration with non-technical stakeholders.

1.4 Co-creation of governance solutions

All these challenges underscore the critical need for practical action points to address them and drive progress in the field while fostering meaningful collaboration between all actors. Particularly with

emerging technologies like in silico trials, a significant challenge lies in creating adaptive and comprehensive regulations that encourage innovation while ensuring safety, privacy, ethics, and societal impact are considered¹⁸. This is where RRI comes in, not just as a strategy to align innovation with societal needs but also as a framework to consider potential governance solutions. In the context of this policy brief, governance refers to the structured framework through which the management and coordination of research and innovation are carried out¹⁹. Possible governance mechanisms entail regulations, principles, standards, efforts to increase security, codes of conduct, impact assessments, or value statements²⁰. A collective anticipatory approach to governance of in silico trial technologies augments the societal integration and responsiveness of innovations and minimises the necessity for regulators to intervene.²¹

Need for interdisciplinary training of all stakeholders: Training and re-training are not just to be considered as facilitators for heightened awareness and collaboration but, more significantly, as essential elements crucial for fostering the trust and expertise indispensable to propel advancements in the field. It is important to note here that training for all stakeholders is required on all facets of in silico trials, not limited to straightforward technical aspects but also social, ethical, and legal aspects.

Need for Patient and Public Involvement: Increased involvement of patients and the public in all research and innovation stages is important to build trust with end-users. This requires a more informed and empowered public that understands the advantages and disadvantages of in silico methods, including the risk-benefit assessment process in *in silico* medicine. Meeting this need will require not only developing material specifically for patients and the public at large but also assisting technology developers in interacting with those stakeholders to inform and train them.

Need for standardisation: There is a clear need for transversal adoption of the ASME VV-40 in a harmonised framework. Research communities themselves play a crucial role in building standards, proposing the outline for a Good Simulation Practice²² and pushing for its full and formal adoption.

Need for regulatory framework: The development of in silico trial technologies emphasises the critical need for a regulatory framework, particularly in integrating in silico trials into the CE marking process for medical devices. Unlike previous discussions on technologies such as AI, which often

¹⁸ Mandel, Gregory N. "Regulating Emerging Technologies." *Law, innovation and technology* 1, no. 1 (2009): 75–92.

¹⁹ Landeweerd, Laurens, David Townend, Jessica Mesman, and Ine Van Hoyweghen. "Reflections on Different Governance Styles in Regulating Science: A Contribution to 'Responsible Research and Innovation.'" *Life sciences, society and policy* 11, no. 1 (2015): 8–8.

²⁰ Stark, Luke, Daniel Greene, and Anna Lauren Hoffmann. "Critical Perspectives on Governance Mechanisms for AI/ML Systems." In *The Cultural Life of Machine Learning*, 257–280. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020.

²¹ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., Geris, L., and Van Hoyweghen, I. Rep. In Silico World WP 5 Responsible Research and Innovation Workshop Report, 2023. Available via public repository: <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740365>

²² Toward Good Simulation Practice: Best practices for the use of computational modelling & simulation in the regulatory process of biomedical products. In: Synthesis Lectures on Biomedical Engineering. Viceconti M. & Emili L. (Eds.), Springer Cham eBook. ISBN: 978-3-031-48283-0, 2024.

revolved around the dichotomy of self-regulation versus 'hard' regulation, there is a necessity for nuanced regulatory adjustments. While anticipating formal regulatory changes, self-regulation mechanisms are important, and they can be driven by a proactive attitude of the in silico medicine community of practice. This can complement the evolving regulatory landscape and set the stage for a more comprehensive exploration of the legislative and policy landscape in the realm of in silico medicine.

Need for streamlined legislative framework: The legal challenges envisioned in the in silico trials framework need to be streamlined. The laws on medical devices and medicinal products mirror the issues encountered in the regulatory framework. Medical device laws do not facilitate nor establish ad hoc references for in silico trials of medical devices; therefore, there is a clear need for regulatory standards. It is important that these standards are acknowledged by legislative bodies so that they can be used to support CE marking and demonstrate compliance with EU law. In addition, the EU's privacy and data protection legal framework has entailed a scattered environment for health data sharing for research. Forthcoming legislation on Data Governance (including the European Health Data Space Regulation) will also have to deal with this problem. Policymakers should collaborate with users to propose concrete solutions with respect to the GDPR while possibly recognising the data-sharing needs of the scientific research community.

Recently, the Coordinator of the In Silico World project, Prof Marco Viceconti, published an opinion piece entitled “[European Union: from the land of rights to the land of rules](#)”. In this, it is suggested that there is a structural problem with any legislation that tries to regulate complex technology-related issues (MDR, GDPR, AI Act, EHDS, for example) and calls for the need for federal agencies that supervise the application of these laws. While this represents a personal opinion, we want to mention it here because it is part of a public debate the In Silico World project initiated.

Call for Ethical Manifesto: An Ethical Manifesto can serve as a compass for ethical decision-making, outlining boundaries and guidelines for the responsible use of in silico models, addressing bias, conflicts, responsibilities, and potential malicious uses in order to demonstrate the community's commitment to responsible research and innovation. Such a manifesto could also address the challenge of poorly informed stakeholders by making them consider and reflect on the wider impact and risks of their work in a responsible manner.

Need for public infrastructures: There is a need for improved accessibility to resources relevant to in silico trial technologies to address the technical challenges related to in silico trial technologies. These resources include data, models, algorithms, compute infrastructure and networks. A public infrastructure, such as the Virtual Human Twin infrastructure being designed by the EDITH Coordination and Support Action²³, can address this need. Such infrastructure is envisioned to enhance transparency, accountability, and responsible innovation within the in silico community.

²³ For more information refer to the website <https://www.edith-csa.eu>

This initiative is furthermore expected to build trust and confidence in the contributions of in silico methodologies across diverse industries and domains.

2 Stakeholder action points and policy recommendations

The presented insights have informed the action points that will follow below. However, it is important to acknowledge that social implications can reoccur at different phases of the lifecycle of an in silico trial, requiring a range of different governance solutions and, thus a wide range of action points to consider. First, general action points and policy recommendations are formulated, followed by action points for specific stakeholder categories. The latter are intended to be taken on by members of said categories, assisted by the in silico medicine developer community to provide input and context (to avoid duplication, said action points are not mentioned in the academia category).

2.1 General action points and policy recommendations

- **Promote and build awareness** about in silico medicine and **engage** through **science communication** and **outreach activities** to a wide range of stakeholders.
- **Educate and train all stakeholders.** Particular attention should also be given to the impact that the uptake of such models can have on clinicians. Furthermore, training on ethical and societal considerations for engineers is necessary to foster interdisciplinary collaboration, in order to leverage trust in the field. The same goes for non-technical stakeholders, such as the patients/carers and the public, who would greatly benefit from gaining more knowledge on the technical aspects of in silico medicine.
- **Recognise and involve patient expertise.** Patients should be recognised as active agents in the development and use of in silico models. As such, it is to be advised to include patients and patient organisations in project teams and advisory boards of different in silico medicine projects. Policies should support patient empowerment by ensuring their right to access and control their health data, as well as their right to be informed and engaged in decisions related to in silico medicine.
- **Encourage collaboration and interdisciplinary research** between different experts in in silico medicine. Integrating a wide range of disciplines in research and innovation, including social sciences and humanities, is an integral commitment of the Horizon Europe program. By bringing in different perspectives, this interdisciplinary approach should ensure a comprehensive understanding of the complex ethical, legal, and social concerns associated with in silico modelling and facilitate the development of models that incorporate diverse perspectives. Research on stakeholders' experiences with in silico medicine (from success stories to concerns) is advised to better understand present needs, expectations, and values.
- **Develop a specific set of recommendations to lower regulatory barriers**, both for policymakers and in silico trial practitioners. This specific focus is being pursued as part of the WP4 activities.
- Continue to foster **collaborations** with regulators and policymakers.

- **Continue to promote** a transitional adoption of VV-40 in Europe as well as the development of an EU harmonised **standard** – a core element of the ISW project.
- **Ensure that underrepresented populations are not excluded** from benefiting from in silico medicine. This needs to be addressed both during the input and output phases. This may involve collaborations with healthcare providers, regulatory bodies, and policymakers to develop strategies for improving access to results from in silico technologies and services. Additionally, the use of in silico (trial) technologies might be the most efficient way to ensure that new products are developed in a scientifically sound manner for a broader scope of populations than the current clinical trial methodologies.
- **Develop manifestos/letters/codes of conduct** that should not only discuss malicious uses or ethical responsibilities of researchers but also acknowledge the limitations of in silico models, the potential risks and ethical conflicts. This should be as detailed as a context-of-use and would enable the fostering of trust.

2.2 Action points for academia

- Focus **research** on the methodological and scientific advances, but also on translational targets, support **entrepreneurship** and consider **regulatory science** early in the process to facilitate clinical/regulatory uptake.
- Perform a **Health Technology Assessment** to provide stakeholders with evidence-based information, ensuring that health policies are safe, effective, patient-centred and cost-efficient.
- Establish **training** programs and **workshops** to integrate in silico medicine into academic curricula in order to increase **awareness**. When doing this, ensure that the training materials educate on both the technical and non-technical (ethical, social, legal) aspects of in silico medicine.
- Continue to **explore the needs, values and expectations** of societal stakeholders by means of surveys, focus groups, or one-on-one interviews.
- Create **information packages** that include resources, case studies, success stories, and best practices to increase awareness and foster trust in in silico medicine and trials. In silico trial technology developers can use these information packages to engage with all stakeholders. These information packages require tailoring to the needs and expectations of each specific group of stakeholders and even specific subgroups within a stakeholder category (e.g. senior citizens in the general public category)
- Encourage **interdisciplinary collaboration** in research and development by, for instance, **including social sciences and humanities** in in silico medicine research projects.

2.3 Action points for Industry

- Establish **(re-)training programs** and workshops to leverage awareness about in silico medicine for industry employees with technical backgrounds (developers) and non-technical backgrounds (regulatory and policy officers, clinical researchers, quality assurance professionals).

- Identify the **strengths, weaknesses, threats and opportunities** of the adoption of in silico trial technologies. In doing this, explore the business opportunities and/or trends that in silico medicine might pose for the biomedical industry.
- Investigate the **needs, expectations, and preferences** of management of companies not yet using in silico trial technologies and explain how in silico medicine can meet these needs. Use **success stories** that quantify the advantage of adopting in silico trial technologies to build **convincing argumentation**.

2.4 *Action points for healthcare professionals*

- Include **training modules** on in silico medicine in the standard educational track as well as in **accredited e-learning materials**. Ensure that the training materials educate on both the technical and non-technical (ethical, social, legal) aspects of in silico medicine. Considering the wider impact of the field is necessary in order to realise its advancement.
- Co-create **information packages** that include resources, case studies, success stories, and best practices for increasing awareness around in silico medicine in general and in silico trials in particular as a way of de-risking new medical products. Information packages should foster trust in in silico technologies by providing education on credibility assessment practices while disclosing the potential risks of these methodologies.

Collaborate with the in silico medicine developer community to gain a deeper understanding of the level of awareness and opinions on in silico medicine amongst healthcare providers. This involves continuously stimulating and participating in engagement activities such as **surveys, focus groups, or individual interviews**.

2.5 *Action points for regulators*

- **Engage** with the in silico trials developers through task forces, working groups, research projects, public hearings, etc., to increase **awareness** of in silico medicine and **foster trust** through continuous **collaboration** and training in all phases of the research and innovation process.
- Increase **expertise exchange** between regulators and developers through joint development of white papers, guidance on executing and documenting credibility assessment and mock submissions intended to **develop the regulatory science** field and build mutual trust.
- Participate in drafting an **ethical manifesto** for the in silico community to stimulate the early assessment of the ethical and social impacts of their technologies by taking proactive steps towards responsible research and innovation. Ensure the possible risks are taken into account.
- Additional action points will emerge from ISW-WP4 work.

2.6 *Action points for health technology assessment agencies and payers*

- Amongst members of the stakeholder group, increase the **awareness** of in silico medicine and foster trust through continuous collaboration and training with in silico trial developers throughout the entire research and innovation process.

- Explore the **strength and weaknesses of Health Technology Assessments** with the aim of informing decisions regarding reimbursement of novel drugs of medical devices developed using in silico trials at a national level.
- Identify the **strengths, weaknesses, threats and opportunities** of in silico trials. In doing this, explore the business opportunities and/or trends that in silico medicine might pose for the payers.

2.7 Action points for policymakers

- Stimulate consumption of information packages to increase **awareness** of and trust in in silico medicine and how it can balance the need for better cures with that of safe products. Create opportunities for training and re-training of policymakers with the necessary technical and social skills on In Silico Trials.
- Encourage the creation of an **ethical manifesto** to prompt the in silico trials developers to consider the ethical and social impacts of their work and technologies. Such a guiding document, developed within the in silico community to provide guidelines to limit potential biases, and outlines the responsibilities and boundaries for the envisioned use of technologies.
- Support the creation of a **Good Simulation Practice** to increase the overall quality of developments in the field and streamline the regulatory process.
- Create a **public infrastructure** to realise the vision of the integrated Virtual Human Twin, facilitating the development of in silico medicine solutions and their credibility assessment.

2.8 Action points for patients and the public at large

- Become an active partner in one's own healthcare process by **consuming information packages and training material** prepared by in silico trials technology developers to increase the awareness of in silico medicine, communicate the benefits and limitations of in silico medicine and foster trust.
- Participate in surveys, focus groups, or one-on-one interviews that allow to **explore the needs, values, expertise and expectations** of societal stakeholders. This will allow to incorporate patient and public input and expertise in the entire decision-making processes to align with the identified values and needs.
- Demand **transparent communication of the benefits and limitations** of in silico medicine for all actors involved in the patient healthcare journey to build trust.

3 Action points identified

3.1 Current status of the action points

Within the In Silico World project context, several of the action points mentioned in the policy brief are already being addressed.

- Training and retraining programs are currently being developed to leverage awareness and understanding of the field of different stakeholders, such as academics, regulators, and healthcare professionals.
 - o Lecturing materials will be made available at the end of the project (2024), and preliminary work on the intended learning outcomes is [available here](#) - supplementary material S3.
- Information packages are being developed targeting specific stakeholder groups (ISW deliverable D5.6 [available here](#) - S1), as well as a toolkit that provides researchers in the field with the necessary tools to engage with stakeholders in order to increase awareness and understanding in order to foster trust in the innovative technologies (VPH InfoKit – available soon – preliminary work [available here](#)) – also see supplementary material S1, S2.
 - o These information packages include resources, case studies, success stories, and best practices for increasing awareness and fostering trust in in silico medicine and trials. It informs stakeholders on the advantages of in silico methods while also addressing potential risks, including information on the risk-benefit profile of in silico medicine.
 - o Multi-media developed by VPH Institute and the community serves as a tool to present this intricate field in easily understandable terms to the general audience. [“Code & Cure: Understanding in silico medicine”](#) is a series of divulgation videos that spread the knowledge of in silico medicine to a larger public audience with accessible animated videos spanning from models to real-world applications.
- A thorough analysis of the regulatory landscape and engagement activities with the regulators is [available here](#), along with specific recommendations for regulators and developers dealing with the regulatory process - supplementary material S4 and S5.
- An ethical manifesto is under development, as brought forward during the workshop. Though more inclusion is needed, social sciences and humanities are increasingly being involved in in silico research projects, which is a step in the right direction - supplementary material S6.
- The In Silico Trials: An Updated SWOT Analysis" presents a comprehensive look at the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for In Silico Trials in healthcare, providing a roadmap to help biomedical companies navigate and adopt these innovative methodologies.

Upcoming:

- Elaborate the policy recommendations in a policy white paper for the wider adoption of in silico trials (ISW deliverable D5.8 in progress as December 15, 2024).

Supplementary material

	Description	Documents, reports, deliverables
S1	Information Package for health care professionals	<p>Public deliverable</p> <p>Rangarajan, J. R., Stanic, G., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Montesarchio, D., & Geris, L. (2024). In Silico World D5.6 - Information Package and Lecturing Materials. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14044934</p>
S2	INFOKIT on stakeholder engagement for modellers	<p>Abstract & presentation</p> <p>Contin, M., Davide Montesarchio, D., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lesage, R., Platonov, A., Stanic, G., De Michele, R., Rangarajan, J. R., & Geris, L. (2024, September 13). An in silico medicine info kit for effective stakeholder engagement. Virtual Physiological Human Conference 2024 (VPH 2024), Stuttgart. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13760091</p> <p>Toolkit: In preparation</p> <p>Multimedia material: VPHi-Animated-Video-Series-Playlist.</p>
S3	Lecture materials for training and re-training	<p>Lecture materials</p> <p>K. Vander Linden, G. Van Looy, G. Davico, M. Viceconti and J. Vander Sloten, “A systematic approach to define intended learning outcomes for different stakeholders for In Silico Trials”, Zenodo, Sep. 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8380239</p> <p>K. Vander Linden, G. Van Looy, G. Davico, M. Viceconti and J. Vander Sloten, “Proposal for curricula to train and retrain different stakeholders on In Silico Trials”, Zenodo, Dec. 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10400657.</p>
S4	Regulatory landscape report	<p>Landscape report</p> <p>Viceconti, M., Pappalardo, F., Curreli, C., Russo, G., & Aldieri, A. (2024). REGULATORY BARRIERS TO THE ADOPTION OF IN SILICO TRIALS (Version v1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948478</p>
S5	Analysis of strengths, weakness, opportunities and threats	<p>SWOT Analysis</p> <p>Viceconti, M. (2024). In Silico Trials: An updated SWOT Analysis. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14011927</p>
S6	Legal and ethical requirements, with implementation guidelines for in silico trial researchers and users	<p>Biasin, E. (2023). In Silico World D9.2 In-depth analysis of legal and ethical requirements. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991233</p> <p>Biasin, E., Corrêa Marcus, A. M., Elhadj, E., & Viceconti, M. (2024). In Silico World D9.3 Implementation guidance and guidelines. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11173758</p>

4 Acknowledgements

This document is an excerpt from In Silico World's Deliverable D5.5, titled "Policy Brief". It serves as a concise summary focusing solely on the key findings in D5.5. The authors gratefully acknowledge invaluable support from the collaborators of the ISW project, in particular the KUL-SSH teams, the VPHi team, and the UNIBO team. We furthermore gratefully acknowledge the collaboration and input from patients and healthcare professionals (via focus groups and the clinical survey).